

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BIGUANIDE WITH TERVALENT METALS. PART II. CHROMIUM BIGUANIDINES.

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A study of the preparation and properties of the salts of chromium *tris*-biguanide with complex inorganic acids has been made. The salts of the tri-basic acids have been observed to form sparingly soluble well-defined crystals and those of the dibasic ones to contain an additional foreign anion.

In Part I of this series the preparation and properties of the chromium *tris*-biguanide base and its salts with simpler acids have been described (Rây and Saha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 670). The constitution of the metal-biguanide complexes has also been discussed in detail in that paper. A study of the salts of chromium *tris*-biguanide with complex inorganic acids has now been made and forms the subject matter of the present communication. Among the salts of the various complex acids studied, it has been observed that those of the tribasic ones form sparingly soluble well-defined crystals; the salts of the di- and monobasic complex acids contain an additional foreign anion. No definite compounds with tetra-basic complex acids could be obtained.

The complex salts studied are the ferricyanide, cobalticyanide, chromi-thiocyanate, cobaltinitrite, chloro-nitroprusside, hydroxo-mercuri-iodide and chloro-bismuthi-iodide. Their composition support the triacidic character of the chromium *tris*-biguanide base. The complex also forms aurichloride and sparingly soluble platinumchloride resembling those of organic amines.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Chromium tris-Biguanide Ferricyanide.—Concentrated solutions of the complex hydrochloride and potassium ferricyanide were mixed together with constant stirring. After a few seconds dark-brown shining needles commenced to separate. These were collected, washed with cold water and dried *in vacuo* over CaCl_2 . The substance is very sparingly soluble in water. {Found: N, 51.48; Cr, 9.16; Fe, 9.66. $[\text{X}]\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ requires N, 51.8g; Cr, 9.17; Fe, 9.87 per cent}.

Where $\text{X} = \text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_3$, and BigH = one biguanide molecule.

Chromium tris-biguanide cobalticyanide was obtained by mixing together concentrated solutions of the complex hydrochloride and potassium cobalticyanide. The rose-coloured crystalline precipitate was

washed first with water and then with alcohol. It was dried as in the previous case. The substance is very sparingly soluble in water. {Found: N, 51.76; Co, 10.26; Cr, 9.33. $[X]Co(CN)_6$ requires N, 51.58; Co, 10.35; Cr, 9.12 per cent}.

Chromium tris-biguanide chromithiocyanate was obtained as a light violet crystalline precipitate when strong solutions of the complex hydrochloride and potassium chromithiocyanate were mixed together. It is almost insoluble in water, but highly soluble in acetone and sparingly in alcohol. {Found: N, 36.28; S, 23.71; Cr, 13.08. $[X]Cr(SCN)_6$ requires N, 36.34; S, 23.73; Cr, 12.85 per cent}.

Chromium tris-biguanide cobaltinitrite was prepared from the complex hydrochloride and sodium cobaltinitrite as described in the previous cases. It forms very sparingly soluble brown crystals. {Found: Co, 8.66; Cr, 7.38. $[X]Co(NO_2)_6$ requires Co, 8.55; Cr, 7.53 per cent}.

Chromium tris-Biguanide Chloro-nitroprusside.—A strong solution of sodium nitroprusside was slowly added to a concentrated solution of the complex hydrochloride. The mixture, on cooling in ice, deposited pink-coloured crystals. The substance is fairly soluble in water and contains also chlorine as an anion. {Found: N, 48.73; Cr, 8.40; Fe, 9.06. $[X]Cl[Fe(NO)(CN)_5]$ requires N, 48.47; Cr, 8.59; Fe, 9.23 per cent}.

Chromium tris-Biguanide Hydroxo-mercuri-iodide.—A concentrated solution of the chromium tris-biguanide hydroxide was treated with a solution of mercuric chloride in potassium iodide (just sufficient to redissolve the mercuric iodide first precipitated). A brick-red crystalline precipitate readily separated from the solution. This was washed and dried as before. The substance is almost insoluble in water, but readily dissolves in alcohol. If the complex hydrochloride be used in place of the base for the preparation of this salt, a substance containing chlorine in the anion is formed. The salt melts at 251° (decomp.). {Found:

N, 13.56; I, 48.93, Cr, 3.52; Hg, 26.45. $[X]_{(HgI_3)_2}^{OH}$ requires N, 13.68; I, 49.67; Cr, 3.38; Hg, 26.07 per cent}.

Chromium tris-biguanide chloro-bismuthi-iodide was obtained as an orange-red precipitate by adding slowly a strong solution of the complex hydrochloride to an acid solution of bisnuth trichloride in an excess of potassium iodide. This was washed and dried as before. The substance is very sparingly soluble in water and contains also chlorine as an

anion. {Found: N, 11.29; I, 56.06; Bi, 22.61; Cr, 2.88. $[X]_{(BiI_4)_2}^{Cl}$ requires N, 11.50; I, 55.68; Bi, 22.91; Cr, 2.85 per cent}.

An orange-coloured silky crystalline precipitate of aurichloride also was obtained by adding a strong solution of aurichloric acid or sodium aurichloride to a concentrated solution of the complex hydrochloride. This is moderately soluble in water.

Similarly an orange-yellow crystalline precipitate, sparingly soluble in water but readily soluble in dilute acids, was obtained from the complex hydrochloride and platinichloric acid or sodium platinichloride.

With potassium ferrocyanide and thiosulphato-pentacyano-potassium cobaltiate the solution of the complex hydrochloride gives granular precipitates of indefinite composition.

Method of Analysis.

The ferricyanide salt was decomposed by heating with concentrated H_2SO_4 . In one part of the prepared solution, iron was estimated volumetrically, and in the other part, the weight of the mixed oxides (Cr_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3) was determined. The nitroprusside compound was also analysed in a similar way.

The cobalticyanide compound was decomposed by heating with concentrated H_2SO_4 . Chromium was precipitated from the resulting solution as $Cr(OH)_3$ by pyridine. In the filtrate cobalt was estimated as $CoSO_4$. The cobaltinitrite compound was also analysed in this way.

In the case of chromithiocyanate compound, chromium was precipitated as $Cr(OH)_3$ after decomposing the compound with concentrated H_2SO_4 . Sulphur was oxidised to sulphate by ammoniacal H_2O_2 and estimated as $BaSO_4$.

The mercuri-iodide compound was dissolved in HCl . Mercury was precipitated as HgS and estimated as such. In the filtrate chromium was estimated as $Cr(OH)_3$. For iodine, the substance was digested with sodium carbonate solution and in the filtrate iodine was estimated as AgI .

The bismuthi-iodide compound was treated with ammoniacal H_2O_2 to oxidise the chromium; the latter was then estimated iodometrically in the filtrate. The residue was dissolved in nitric acid and from the solution bismuth was precipitated as basic carbonate. Iodine was estimated as in the case of the mercuri-iodide compound, but the precipitate of silver iodide was digested with dilute ammonia to remove the silver chloride simultaneously precipitated.

Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method in all the cases except that of nitroprusside. In the latter compound it was estimated by Dumas' method.